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**ISSUES OF TWO YEARS B.Ed. PROGRAM WHICH MAY REFLECT ON
FOUR YEAR B. ED. PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

Teacher education in present century faces challenges of providing literacy and knowledge required for progress of the society. Justice Verma commission (2012) recommended that B.Ed. program should be two year with the adequate provision to branch out in specializations in curriculum studies, policies, finance and foundational studies. Recently NCTE regulation 2014 made a radical change in teacher training program particularly in B.Ed. program and proposed two year B.Ed. program which has been came into the force from academic session 2015-17. The course structure of the two year-B.Ed. program offers a comprehensive coverage of themes and rigorous field engagement with the child, school and community. Recently MHRD announced that Four-year integrated B. Ed course will be launched from the upcoming academic session. The four-year B. Ed courses are B.A. - B.Ed., B.Sc.-B.Ed. and B.Com- B.Ed. In the place of the popular two year B. Ed. course, HRD has introduced a four-year integrated teacher training B. Ed course. Now, B. Ed course is of two-year duration. In the present study the investigator made an attempt to study the problem faced by the student- teachers during two year B.Ed. program which will reflect on the four year B. Ed program under Mangalore University. Total 86 student-teachers were taken from six colleges affiliated to Mangalore University representing. Questionnaire for collecting the data and percentage method for interpretation was used. This study revealed that student-teachers face many problems after the implementation of two year B.Ed. course which may reflect on 4 year B. ed. Not only the student-teachers but the teacher educators and administration itself face different problems.

Key Words: Two Year B.Ed. Program, Four year B. Ed program, student-Teacher

I. INTRODUCTION:

Teacher education is an integral part of education process. The quality of teachers training

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program determines the success of educational system. Teacher education in the present century is a challenge of providing literacy and knowledge required for progress of the society. The quality of education depends upon the quality education of teachers. The qualitative aspects of education depend on the character, qualification and personality of the teachers. The role of the teachers is very important for the formation of the healthy nation. In order to develop the quality of the teacher, student-teachers training is very necessary. The bachelor of education (B.Ed.) prepares the quality teachers to improve the quality of school education and also increase the learning of children. In this direction efforts were made by implementing the various recommendations by different commissions and committees in India. NCTE has also brought out national curriculum framework for teacher education during 1978, 1988, 1998 and 2009 which recommended improving the quality of B.Ed. program.

II New Four-year B .Ed program Structure

There is a saying that "Those who can do; and those who cannot, teach," which means people will take up the teaching profession who don't possess skills in any particular industry. If this is the case to the education will not improve. To make teaching profession of choice instead of leftover, the government has rolled out a four year integrated B. Ed Program. I felt that the existing two year B.Ed. program is general in nature and unable to prepare quality teachers. Since B.Ed. is a professional course, skills, techniques and strategies are needed than extensive theoretical framework of the curriculum. The four year B.Ed. program as suggested by NCTE, 2018 can prepare the quality teacher and fulfill the needs of the students. It is this feeling that has urged to take up the present study entitled, **“Issues of two years B. Ed. which may reflect on four year B. Ed. Program.”** It is expected that this study will be able to make some significant contribution in the field of teacher education. The structure of the program is

- To improve the quality of teaching at all levels of education, the MHRD has proposed the 4-year B. Ed program in February 2019 and will be offered at two levels -Pre-Primary to Primary level and Upper Primary to Secondary Level.
- B. Ed program Available in Three Streams. Interested candidates can opt. the course in three streams. Candidates can choose either BA-B. Ed, B. Sc -B. Ed and B, Com- B. Ed. One can choose this integrated four-year B. Ed program which will save one year instead of five years (3 years bachelor degree + 2 years B. Ed).
- Candidates can join the 4-year B. Ed program after studying in their Class 12(PUC). The

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National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) is working on the B. Ed curriculum.

- The government will be providing grace time to candidates who have completed their bachelor's or master's degree. They can continue the two-year B. Ed program or three-year integrated B. Ed + M. Ed course.
- This course is mandatory to become a teacher at the secondary (Classes 6 to 10) and higher secondary (10+2 or Classes 11 and 12).
- Every year, the entrance exam will be conducted in May/June.
- Candidates are advised to check the B. Ed syllabus before taking up the course.
- The two-year B. Ed course was divided into four semesters. There is no announcement yet regarding semesters of 4-year B. Ed.
- The B. Ed curriculum would be prepared by the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE).
- NCTE has invited applications from interested institutions to include B. Ed- 4 years'

III. REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE:

S. Nalawade-Jadhav Vandana (2015) found that institutions faced many constraints in admission procedure, infrastructure management, teacher's recruitment and school internship after the implementation of two year B. Ed program. Ravinder Kumar Kamboj (2015) found that the teacher-educators have undergone more stress during two year B.Ed. functioning. R. Jaya Kumar (2016) concluded that students from any field can do B. Ed but there is no job security for such students. Pargat Singh Garcha (2016) found gap in theoretical and practical framework of two year B.Ed. program. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has scrapped the two-year Bachelor of Education program (B. Ed) which was introduced three years ago. In the place of the popular education-related course, HRD has introduced a **four-year integrated teacher training B. Ed degree**.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of the present study are as follow:

- To find out the facilities provided by the self-financed institutions to the pupil-teachers.
- To find out the availability of teaching and non-teaching staff in self-financed institutions.
- To find out the availability of appropriate study materials in self-financed institutions.
- To give an idea about the structure of four year B. Ed program.

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- To reflect on the problems of two year B.Ed. that may affect on the four year B. Ed program

V. METHODOLOGY:

The present study was based on survey method, using Google forms. The B. Ed. student-teachers of six B. Ed colleges comprised the population of this study. Total 100 student-teachers from the recognized government, private, aided both urban and rural B.Ed. colleges were taken. Questionnaire was used for collecting the data and percentage method was used for interpretation. Questionnaire was used for knowing the problems of pupil-teachers of two year B.Ed. program. Questionnaire contains different questions according to objectives of the present study under dimensions namely (a) facilities (b) Teaching and non-teaching staff (c) Study material. Percentage was used to analyze the collected data and to verify the result.

VI. Hypothesis:

- Student teachers are less satisfied by the Facilities provided by the institutions.
- Availability of adequate teaching and non-teaching staff in many colleges are not sufficient.
- Student teachers are less satisfied by the availability of appropriate study materials.
- Availability of adequate Building requirement as per NCTE Norms.

VII. Delimitations of the Study

The delimitations of the present study are as follow:

- -The investigation was delimited to only Mangalore University.
- -The study was restricted to the pupil-teachers studying in six B.Ed. colleges of the Mangalore University.
 - This study was conducted only at surface level. It was not an „in-depth“ study.
- -The researcher has concentrated on very few variables like staff, Building, facilities and study materials.

VIII. FINDINGS:

The major findings of the study revealed that there were many problems faced by the student-teachers after implementation of two Year B.Ed. program, i.e. most of the pupil-teachers were not satisfied by FOUR Year B.Ed. programs. The present study indicates that 52.3% student-teachers consider it as not suitable and 41.1 consider it as suitable and 5.8% student teachers have different opinion about the issue. When the question on quality of four year B. Ed. Was asked 60.5% agree

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about quality enhancement and not 39.5% disagree with it. It was found that 52.3% student-teachers were satisfied and 47.7% student-teachers were not satisfied by the availability of adequate teaching and non-teaching staff according to two year B.Ed. programs in institutions. It is also found that 69.8% student-teachers were satisfied and 30.2% student-teachers were not satisfied by facilities provided by the institutions to the student-teachers. It means most of the private colleges provide adequate facilities to the student-teachers. It was also found that 87.2% student-teachers were satisfied and 12.8% pupil-teachers were not satisfied by the availability of appropriate study materials according to Two Year B.Ed. Program in institutions. Around 54.7% student-teachers were satisfied with laboratories available and 45.3 % student-teachers were not satisfied. It is also found that 82.6.8% student-teachers were satisfied and 17.4% student-teachers were not satisfied by library facilities provided by the institutions to the student-teachers. Even it is also found that 69.8% student-teachers were satisfied and 30.2% student-teachers were not satisfied by the ICT facilities provided by the institutions to the student-teachers. It is also found that 72.1.8% student-teachers were satisfied and 27.9% student-teachers were not satisfied by the infrastructure facilities provided by the institutions to the student-teachers. The present study indicated that there were many problems faced by the student-teachers after TWO year B.Ed. program. In most of the conditions student-teachers were not satisfied by the present B.Ed. program which will affect and reflect on four year B. Ed program. In general it is observed that there are no sufficient staff and non teaching staff as per NCTE norms. In many of the colleges there is lack of resources, funds, and infrastructure and basic facilities to run the institute. Some of the colleges are offering B .Ed, degree on correspondence mode though they are regular colleges. It is proved that when the question like, working while pursuing regular B. Ed program, around five percent agreed that they are working. Some of the colleges under Mangalore University are not fulfilling NCTE norms.

It is also an observation that no colleges under Mangalore University have come forward to start four year B. Ed program. The problem of qualified staff with two masters like masters in concerned subject with M. Ed is difficult to get. There is a problem of strength if any one stream or all the three streams are started. Still there is no clear cut information available about four year B.Ed. program. The degree colleges can start four year B. Ed program by appointing qualified staff and can manage with existing resources.

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IX. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION:

- It is a humble attempt in this direction to assess the level of knowledge and problems of pupil-teachers after implementation of four year B.Ed. program.
- It is very much essential for acquiring the knowledge and to solve the problems of pupil-teachers after implementation of four year B.Ed. program.
- It is a humble request to focus on the problems of two year B. Ed before offering four B. Ed program

X. CONCLUSION:

Even after facing many controversies, MHRD has proposed the four year B.Ed. program with the motive to properly train the pupil-teachers as two year B.Ed. program was not found to be enough effective. But present study revealed that most of the pupil-teachers face many different problems after implementation of two year B.Ed. program. Even the teachers and the administrations of respective institutions found great difficulty in their work after this decision which will reflect on four year B. Ed program.

Table-1: The Teacher trainee’s responses on the two years B. Ed. Program

Sl. No.	Question	Yes	No	other	Total
01	Does the 4 Year B. Ed program is correct/suitable?	41.9	52.3	5.8	100
02	Does the Quality of student trainees will improve by increase of 4 years?	60.5	39.5	-	100
03	Does your college have sufficient staff and non teaching staff as per norms?	52.3	47.7	-	100
04	Does your college have sufficient facilities required?	69.8	30.2	-	100
05	Does your college have sufficient study materials required?	87.2	12.8	-	100
06	Do you have laboratories required in the college?	54.7	45.3	-	100
07	Do you have sufficient library books in the college?	82.6	17.4	-	100
08	Do you have sufficient ICT facilities in the college?	69.8	30.2	-	100
09	Are you an employee in any institution while studying ?	4.7	95.3	-	100
10	Does your college has proper infrastructure?	72.1	27.9	-	100

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Issues of two years B. Ed. which may reflect on four year B.Ed. Program

Does the Quality of student trainees will improve by increase of 4 years?
86 responses

Does the Quality of student trainees will improve by increase of 4 years?
86 responses

Does your college have sufficient staff and non teaching staff as per norms?
86 responses

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Does your college have sufficient facilities required?

86 responses

Does your college have sufficient study materials required?

86 responses

Do you have laboratories required in the college?

86 responses

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Do you have sufficient library books in the college?

86 responses

Do you have sufficient ICT facilities in the college?

86 responses

Are you an employee in any institution

86 responses

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Do you have the proper infrastructure?
86 responses

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